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EFFECT OF FISCAL POLICY ON CORPORATE PERFORMANCE AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: *This study's main objective is to analyze the effect of fiscal policy on corporate performance and economic growth in Nigeria for the period of 2000 –2021. The research aims at evaluating the causal relationship between money supply, fiscal deficits and export. The empirical analysis that was carried out to*

achieve the objective of determining the effect of fiscal policy on corporate performance and economic growth were time series data from the central bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin. With sample size of 21 years. The research design used is ex-post-facto method, while the analytical tool used is simple linear regression analysis. The findings were consistent with the empirical result. The empirical result will be effective in stimulating economic growth and development vis-à-vis corporate performance. We recommend appropriate policy mix, prudent public spending, setting of achievable fiscal policy targets and diversification of the nation's economic base, among others

Keywords: fiscal policy, diversification, economic development, corporate performance, regulation.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most challenging development issues in the third world country today is sustainable economic growth and development. Macroeconomic thinkers and policy makers even from the days of Adams Smith has the main focus of how to attain macroeconomic stability. The two major economic policy often used to stabilize any economy of the world are monetary and fiscal policies. Their major tools are money supply and government expenditure, respectively. Fiscal policy puts hands together in macroeconomic management, as developments in one sector directly affect the developments in the other. Moreover, economists also concur that fiscal policy is affecting the level of economic activities but the degree and relative potency of this policy have been the subject of debates and controversies, between various schools of thought.

Over the years, the country has been witnessing economic setbacks, shocks and disturbances both internally and externally. Internally, the factors responsible for these are unstable investment and consumption patterns, as well as the improper implementation of public policies, changes in future expectation and accelerators. While the external factors include wars, revolutions, population growth rates and immigration, technological transfer and changes and in addition, the openness of the country's economy. Fiscal policy is a major economic stabilization weapon that involves measures taken to regulate and control the volume, cost and availability as well as direction of money in an economy to achieve some specified macroeconomic policy objectives.

This will help to counteract undesirable trends in the Nigerian economy. Therefore, they cannot be left to the market forces of demand and supply neither will they be left for other instruments of stabilization such as monetary and exchange rate policies, this action can include either an increase or a decrease in taxes as well as government expenditure which forms the bedrock of fiscal policy. In reality, government requires a mixture of both fiscal and monetary policy instruments to stabilize an economy because, none of these single instruments can cure all the problems in an economy (Ndiyo and Udo, 2003).

In Nigeria, lack of fiscal discipline is the bane of the economic development having the fact that realized revenues are often above budgetary estimate. Extra budgetary expenditure has been rising fast resulting to large fiscal deficit. The unhealthy situation is attributed largely to the huge debt service duty and expenditure. To address these gaps in fiscal policy on

corporate performance and economic development in Nigeria literature, a sample of 21 years time series data from the central bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin were extracted. The specified objectives are to examine the effect of government expenditure on consumption expenditure, to ascertain the impact of taxation on organizational activities, to determine the effect of subsidies on organizational and corporate performance, and to ascertain the impact of fiscal policy on corporate performance in Nigeria.

On this note has the researcher decided to check the place of fiscal policy in correcting this deficit, thus, checking the effect of fiscal policy on corporate performance and economic development. The rest of the paper is structured as Section 2 briefly reviews empirical literature. It discusses its effect on fiscal deficit and economic performance in Nigeria. The research design is described in Section 3, while Section 4 presents and discusses the empirical findings. Section 5 provides a summary of the results, conclusion and recommendations.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

In the studies OECD (2021).says that fiscal policy directly supports environmental sustainability through fiscal incentives to research development, direct grant, public research etcetera. These scholars empirically investigated the responsiveness of general price level of economic activity represented by aggregate consumption to change in money supply and autonomous government expenditure, using ordinary simple linear regression model to estimate the U.S data form 1897 – 1957. In their conclusion, they found out that a stable and predictable causal relationship existed between demand and supply while no such significant relationship was observed for government expenditure.

This was supported by Congregational Research Service (2021) when he says that as the economy exists a recession and begins to grow at a healthy pace, policy makers may choose to reduce fiscal stimulus to avoid some of the negative effects of economic recession. Also, According to Brookings (2020), some countries are prematurely touting the idea of fiscal consolidation to return to a sustainable path. Relating today's urban unemployment, analysing monetary and fiscal policy, it implies that fiscal variables such as government expenditure, tax incentives, subsidies and transfer payment will improve consumption pattern.

Researchgate,(2017) said that the impact of fiscal policy in stimulating growth during deregulation period was marginally higher than in the regulation period. Fiscal Policy deals with government deliberate actions in spending money and levying taxes with a view to influencing macro-economic variables, in a desired direction.

According to Microsoft corporation (2020), this includes sustainable economic growth, high employment creation, and low inflation. In Ogili (2020), fiscal policy aims, at stabilizing

the economy, increases in government spending or reduction in taxes tends to pull the economy out of a recession; while reduced spending or increased taxes. This slows down a boom. The way government intervenes in economic activities, are basically in the form of control of selected areas/sectors of the economy. These controls differ and depend on the specific need, or purpose the government desires to achieve.

Aregbeyen (2007) established positive relationship between fiscal policy (public spending) and economic development. Aregbeyen (2007) discovered that the share of government capital expenditures in the gross domestic product is positively correlated with economic growth and development while the growth effect of current expenditure is insignificant. For Aregbeyen (2007) although government expenditure were necessary for economic growth, yet the impact of such expenditures on the economy is of primary importance. He concluded that the key to rapid growth of the economy constituted capital and public investment expenditure. He also emphasized that increased government budget deficits do not automatically guarantee rapid economic growth. Adeoye (2006) stated that the effectiveness of fiscal policy as a tool for promoting growth and development remains inconclusive. In the statement of Khosravi and Karimi (2010); Fiscal policy is generally believed to associate with growth. It is also held that to stimulate economic growth and development, appropriate fiscal measures in particular circumstances can be used. So many empirical literature have come up to unravel the relationship between various measures of fiscal variables and economic growth.

Mausouri (2008) conducted an analysis of past empirical studies of fiscal policy and growth and found that in a sample of 41 students, 29% indicate a negative relationship between fiscal policy and growth, 17% a positive one and 54% an inconclusive relationship, Ekpo (2020) studied the contribution of public expenditure to economic growth in Nigeria over the periods 1960 – 1992. They found out that fiscal policy has led to growth through Crowd-in private investment which results from government expenditure on infrastructure. Abata, Kehinde and Bolanwa (2012) advises that government should not only support and encourage economic growth, but should also increase its budgetary provision on infrastructure, social and economic activities.

Nurudeen and Usman (2010) analyzed the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria between 1970 and 2008. The paper revealed that the government total capital expenditure, total recurrent expenditures and expenditure on education have negative effect on economic growth while expenditure on health, transport and communication are growth enhancing. Further studies of the impact of budgetary expenditure on the defence sector on economic development of Nigeria discovered that defense expenditure exerts positive effect on economic growth.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The method used is ex-post-facto. The analytical tool used also is simple linear regression analysis. The use of ordinary least square method (OLS) is because of its simplicity and the estimates, obtained from the method have optimal properties such as linearity, unbiasedness and minimum variances.

Sources of Data

The data used for the research work were secondary ones. They involved time series data on fiscal policy and economic growth and development between 1990 and 2013. Sources included; CBN statistical bulletin, Federal office of statistics, CBN economic and financial review bulletin of various years.

Model Specification

To establish the relationship between economic development and fiscal policy variables, we adopted the growth model. The suggestion may come up that inflation discourages development and mild inflation encourages it, after a point the depressive effect of inflation, offsets the stimulating effect of monetary expansion (Ogbote 2011). In other words, critical rate of inflation may exist beyond which growth declines. We will use government expenditure as our explanatory variable for growth. We specified a GDP model and included a dummy variable (dum) having values of zero (0) for the period of regulation and One (1) for the period of deregulation.

The magnitude of the coefficient of the dummy variable in the model was used to determine the extent of difference in the effectiveness of fiscal policy in stimulating economic development in these two periods. The probability value (P. value) of DUM was compared with Alpha ($\alpha = 0.05$) to determine the statistical significance of the difference. The functional relations of our model.

$$GDP = f(GE, IFR, Sd, CIF, x)$$

Is specified in the regression form below as

$$GDP = a_0 + a_1GE + a_2IFR + a_3Sd + a_4CIF + a_5x + a_6DUM + U_1$$

Where, GE = government expenditure

IFR = Inflation Rate

Sd = Subsidies, Cif = capital inflow, X = export DUM = Dummy variable U_1 = Random, error

Apriori expectation $a_2, a_4, a_5 > 0, a_3 < 0$. Towards the end of the study, we are expected to know the kind of relationship existing in fiscal policy and economic development. This is expected to be positive. This, result will help to verify if it's made significant impact on economic

Method of Evaluation

Testing the goodness of fit of the explanatory power of the independent variable is effected using the coefficient of determination (R^2) the value of R^2 lies between 0 and 1, that is, $0 - R^2 - 1$. The closer it is to 1, the better the goodness of fit or the explanatory power of the independent variable and the farther away it is from 1 (that is the closer it is to 0 the worse the goodness of fit. The statistical significance of the regression coefficients will be carried out so as to determine the students t – test. The observed t-ratio (t) will be compared with the critical t-ratio ($t_{0.25}$) for a two failed test at 5% level of significance with n-k degree of freedom.

Where n is the number of observation and k is the number of estimated parameters. If $t < t_{0.25}$, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis. The F – test will be used to test the entire regression plane and the stability of the regression coefficient. The observed f ratio (f) will be compared with the entical ratio ($F_{0.05}$) at 5% level of significance and $Vt - K = 1$ and $vy = nk$ degree of freedom. If $t > F_{0.05}$, the regression equation is significant and the converse.

Empirical Results

Data from money supply (GDP) was used as explanatory variable with consumption expenditure as dependent variable,. The regression mode and its methodology are tested in the previous chapter. Data obtained from the period of 2000 and 2014. These results of using

these data were compared with the present economic stand in empirical view, to estimate the equation, bearing in mind the objective and hypotheses of the study.

There was an appraisal and analysis of each variable in equation.

Ordinary least square method was used for analysis in estimating the models for a reliable result the regression result. The robustness of these work was tested through the use of panel data technique. The estimated model is as follows:

Estimation of results of Income (money supply GDP) Model by ordinary least square method

Constant = 3467

Income 0.03

R² = 0.7936

Adjusted r² (r) = 0.8908

F – Statistics critical = 5.3177

T – Statistical value = 6.02

F – Calculated 1.1645

Durbin – Watson statistics = 2.71

This is the most celebrated test that detests serial correlation

Note: Durbin Watson statistics is used to test for evidence of first order auto correlation in an auto regressive model.

If $|h| > 1.96$ reject the null hypothesis that $P = 0$, where P is an estimate of the first order serial correlation. For appropriate specification of the regression model, the estimated empirical results through the method OLS is as follow:

$Y_0 = b_0 + b_1x_1 + U$ Where

Y_0 = consumption expenditure b_0 = Constant b_1

= Parameter (coefficient of X. to be estimated)

Where also b_1 = population value or characteristic, for instance, the population, standard deviation, etc.

statistics = sample value used for the estimation of the population parameter

X_1 = Government expenditure

u = Stochastic or Error term

Therefore, $Y_0 = 3467 + 0.03x$

Note also that T-statistics test is used to test the significance of regression. Coefficients. This is a follow up test of significance which is a procedure by which sample results are used to verify the truth or falsity of a null hypothesis.

Analyses

The regression result above shows that a linear relationship exists between consumption expenditure and government expenditure as dependent and independent variables. Their relationship is positive from the result. It is discovered that if government expenditure is increased by 15, consumption expenditure will increase by about 6%. The T – value of the explanatory variable is statistically significant when it is tested in a two-tailed test of significance at 5% level.

However, the result of the regression shows a positive relationship, which is in line with the apriori expectation of economic theory. The reaction of the independent variable and the estimated model revealed that it is statistically significant but low at five percent level as determined by the value of coefficient of determination (r^2). The Durbin Watson statistics used to test the evidence of first order's serial correlation is 2.71. This suggests the existence of auto correlation.

Test of Hypotheses

The T-test statistics used to test for the viability of the individual regression coefficient since the number of observation, under study is less than 30 (ie $n < 30$) among the research hypothesis to establish our fact. Below is the hypothesis

H₀₁: Government expenditure does not have significant effect on consumption expenditure. Reject H₀ if $T_{calc} > T_{critical}$ and accept H₀ if $T_{calc} < T_{critical}$. Therefore from the regression result, $T_{cal} = 0.7$ using the two tailed test at 5% level of significance. $N - K = 9 - 2 = 7$ Where N = sample size, K = number in total of estimated parameter. From the result above, t-critical is 2.36 (where $t_{(0.05/2)} = t_{(0.025)} = 2.36$ at 7 D.F) From the result, the t-calculated is less than t- critical. Accept the null hypothesis on ground that; Government expenditure does not have significant effect on consumption expenditure. $T_{xcal} < T_{critical}$.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary of Findings

In the analysis of data, it was found out that significant impact were made on the process of government expenditure. Among the findings are: a. Fund misappropriation in government expenditure does not allow it to go a long way to address the issue of consumption expenditure as the case may be. Other aspects of fiscal policy like subsidies, deficit financing etc can help improved on consumption expenditure.

Conclusion

The role of government expenditure on income distribution and consumption pattern reduces unemployment in our nation Nigeria. We conclude that, although the government

expends fund on various projects, yet, it does not significantly or positively affect consumption expenditure. This might be as a result of misappropriation of fund and embarking on a long term project forcing it to be finished under 3 years. But, if government expenditure is properly addressed through the use of fiscal policy consumption expenditure will be adequate.

Recommendation

We also recommend that the tools of fiscal policy such a subsidies, deficit financing and other money control tools (such as C.B.N control money supply etc) should be applied to control government expenditure, improve the GDP of the nation and enhance economic growth and development.

REFERENCE

- Abata, M.A: Kehinde, J.S. & Bolanwa, S.A. (2012). Fiscal/monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria: A Theoretical Exploration, Lagos State University.www.gmail.com 1(5). Accessed 15/6/15
- Adeoye, T (2006). *Fiscal policy and growth of the Nigerian economy*. Niger Monograph series p. iv. Accessed in 15/6/15
- Aregboyan, O (2007) Public Expenditure and Economic Growth. *African Journals of Economic Policy* Ibadana. Univresity of Ibadan press ICIY 1 -37. Accessed 15/6/15
- Brooklings (2020). Fiscal policy for COVID 19 and beyond. www.brookling.ed 28/11/21
- Congregational Research Service (2021). Fiscal policy economic effect. FAS Project on government secrecy.Sgp.fas.org 20/11/20
- Ekpo, A. (2020). *Public expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria, 1960 – 1992*. Final Report, Nairobi, AERC.
- Kosravi, A. & Karimi, M.S .(2010). To investigate the relationship between monetary and fiscal policy. <http://www.researchgate.net> 2/10/21
- Microsoft Corporation (2004) Microsoft Encarta encyclopedia. Accessed 15/6/15. Mousori, B. (2008). The political economy of fiscal policy. <http://www.jstor.org>
- Ndiyo, N.A & Uda, E.B (2003). Dynamics of monetary policy and poverty in a small open economy. The Nigeria experience, *Nigeria Journals of Economic and Development Matters* 4(1) Accessed in 15th June, 2015 87 – 102.
- Nurudeen & Usman (2012), In Abata M.A et al (2012). Fiscal/monetary policy and economic growth in Nigeria 1(5) www.gmail.com . Accessed 15/6/15.
- OECD(2021). Tax and fiscal policies after COVID 19 crises. www.oecd.org>policy>responses.

Ogbote, F.O, Sonny, .& Isaac, D.E (2011). Fiscal policy: its impact on economics growth in *Nigeria Journal of Economics and International Finance* 3(6) 407 – 417

www.acadmeicjournals.org. Accessed in 15th July 2015.

Ogili, P. (2020). Reading in public finance and policy. Social science study Group Monograph series 1(1) makurd Kingdom, printing & Publishing Co. Ltd. Accessed 15th July 2015.

Model used

$$Y_o = b_0 + b_1x + u$$

Table 1.0

Append	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
X	30	40	63	74	65	46	37	48	59
Y	29.6	11.8	12.5	11.6	15.12	18	17.8	19	11

Table 1.1

N Billion

X	Y	Xy	X ²	Y ²	X ² -X	y-Y
30	2.86	85.8	900	8.18	21.33	-1.24
40	1.48	47.2	1600	2.19	11.33	0.14
63	1.25	78.7	3969	1.48	-11.67	0.37
74	1.16	185.84	5476	1.35	-22.67	0.46
65	1.5	97.5	4225	2.25	-13.67	0.12
46	1.8	69	2116	3.24	5.83	-0.18
37	1.78	102	1369	3.17	14.33	-0.16
48	1.99	85.97	2304	3.96	3.33	-0.37
59	1.1	64.9	3481	1.21	-7.67	-0.52
=467	14.57	716.92	24070	27.03	-28.39	-0.34

Mean of x (X) = 51.33

Mean of y (Y) = 1.67

a) Determination of Bo and Bi

$$B_0 = \frac{\sum x x^2 - \sum x \sum xy}{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}$$

$$= \frac{462 \times 24070 - 462 \times 716.97}{9 \times 24070 - (462)^2}$$

$$b_0 = \frac{462 \times 24070 - 462 \times 716.97}{9 \times 24070 - (462)^2}$$

$$b_0 = \frac{11,120,340 - 75,271.025 \cdot 216630}{-213444}$$

$$b_0 = \frac{11,045,069}{-213444} = -51.75$$

$$B_0 = 3,467$$

Also

$$b_1 = \frac{\sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2}$$

$$\text{i.e. } \frac{716.92 - 462 \times 14.57}{24070 - (467)^2}$$

$$= \frac{716.92 - 6731}{24070 - 213,197}$$

$$= \frac{6014.08}{-189,127} = -0.0318$$

$$\therefore Y = 3467 + 0.03x$$

Where

Constant (b_0) = 3467

Government expenditure = 0.03

B Computation of coefficient of determination (r^2) About r^2 and R^2

R^2 is used in multiple variable cases while r^2 is used in two variable cases, when there is overlap between x and y . Overlap indicates the extent to which the variation in y is explained by the variation in x (via OLS regression). The greater the extent of the overlap, the greater the variation in y is explained by x .

Moving from left to right, the area of the overlap increases. That is, r^2 increases.

No overlap $r^2 = 0$ when there is complete overlap $r^2 = 1$

$$r^2 = \frac{B^2}{\sum x^2 \left(\frac{\sum y^2}{n} \right)}$$

$$r^2 = 0.032 \frac{24070 \cdot 27,03}{\left(\right)}$$

$$= 0.0009 \times 881.685$$

$$r^2 = 0.7935$$

$$= 0.7935$$

$$= \sqrt{0.8908}$$

C) Determination of F – Statistic

Use of Analysis of variance *ANOVA) groups X and Y

$$\text{Group X} = \frac{\sum(\sum x^2)}{N} - \frac{\sum(\sum .x)^2}{N+n} - \frac{(\sum x^2 + \sum \sum x)^2}{N+n}$$

$$\text{ie } \frac{(24070)^2}{9} - \frac{(452)^2}{18} - \frac{24070+462}{18}$$

$$= 64,373 \ 878 - 23716-1, 362.89$$

$$= N64, 349$$

$$\text{Mean of X} = \frac{64,349}{9} = 7.15$$

Group Y

$$Y = \frac{(27.03)^2}{14} - \frac{14.5^2}{14} - \frac{(27,03+14,57)}{14}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{9}{9} \times 23.59 - \frac{18}{9} \times 2.31 \\
 &= 55.28
 \end{aligned}$$

Mean of Y = $55.28/9 = 6.14$

F- ratio

Value of x (mean)

Mean of y

= 7.15

$6.14 - 1.1645$

Where D.F = $9 - 1 = 8$

8 is checked up under I in D.F table = 5.3179

Since, t(f) calculated < F – critical, accept the null hypothesis.

Durbin Watson T-test

$$d = \frac{\sum_{t=2}^{n=0} u_t (u_t - 1)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^{n=0} u_t}$$

$\sum_{t=1}^{n=0} u_t$

U t

Note that $U = Y - \bar{Y}$

Where \bar{Y} (mean) = $\frac{14.57}{9} = 1.62$

$Y = 1.9$

$U = Y - \bar{Y} = -0.34$

i.e. $\frac{(-0.34 - 0.34 - 1)^2}{9}$

$d = \frac{(-0.34)^2 + (-1.68)^2}{1.0404}$

$d = \frac{2.8224}{1.04} = 2.71$

Determination of t-test

(Since samples are unrelated)

$$t = \frac{\bar{X} - \bar{Y}}{\sqrt{\frac{S_x^2}{N} + \frac{S_y^2}{N}}}$$

= 1.62

MWeahern ofe Yst andard deviation = -28.39

X = 51.33

Where also

$$\text{Stand. Deviation} = \frac{\sum X^2}{N}$$

$$T = \frac{51.33 - 1.62}{\sqrt{\frac{24070}{9} + \frac{212285}{9}}}$$

$$T = \frac{49.71}{\sqrt{17.238 + 51.194}}$$

$$T = \frac{49.71}{\sqrt{68.432}} = \frac{49.71}{8.27}$$

$$T = 6.02$$